

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA):IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Medicated Tattoos: - A Novel Drug Delivery System

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 12 Sep 2024

Accepted: 16 Sep 2024

Published: 22 Sep 2024

Keywords:

Transdermal drug delivery,
Medicated tattoos, Medical
alert, Skin penetration,
Biosensors..

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13825045

ABSTRACT

Transdermal drug delivery devices could be used to provide medication and offer the benefit of dispersing a therapeutically appropriate dose of medication across the skin of a patient. One of the newest developments in transdermal drug administration is medical tattoos. Studies show that people have used tattoos for a variety of purposes throughout history, such as a symbol of status, a commitment to a particular religion or spirituality, a decoration for valor, sexual temptation, and an expression of love. Syphilis, tetanus, TB, and herpes have all been linked to tattooing in recent years in a number of recorded cases. Many of these illnesses were caused by tattoo artists holding needles in their mouths or mixing saliva with ink. Given that tattoos are fashionable among teenagers, medicated tattoos are quickly becoming a highly common drug delivery method.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past twenty years, tattooing has garnered remarkably significant prominence. Its root term, "tatu," is to brand anything for symbolic representation or identification. Studies show that people have used tattoos for a variety of purposes throughout history, such as a symbol of status, a commitment to a particular religion or spirituality, a decoration for valor, sexual temptation, and an expression of love. Syphilis, tetanus, TB, and

herpes have all been linked to tattooing in recent years in a number of recorded cases. In more recent times, tattooing has also made its way into the medical profession (scar concealment, endoscopic gastrointestinal tattooing, permanent makeup tattooing, and radiation field marking. Recently, tattooing has become popularly employed in the medical industry as a method of drug delivery (corneal tattooing, gastrointestinal

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

tattooing during endoscopy, permanent makeup tattooing, scar camouflaging, or radiation field marking). Many of these illnesses were brought on by tattoo artists holding needles in their mouths or mixing saliva with ink.

Figure 1 Medicated Tattoo

Modern Tattooists use the Following Steps:

1. First, a unique moveable shaft called the "needle bar" is attached with solder to the needles before being put into a stainless-steel tube that acts as the "grip" of the device.
2. After that, these goods are sterilized.

3. The tip of the needle bar is then submerged in various pigments to trace a design and fill it with colors ranging from 1 to 14.
4. Finally, the needles pierce the epidermis, the skin's outermost layer, and reach the dermis by protruding out of the base of the needle bar and tube assembly, which is attached onto a direct current (DC) powered machine that vibrates the needle bar.

As a result of technical development, traditional tattooing has been transformed into a transdermal medicine delivery system. Transdermal drug delivery systems are a potential source of drug delivery through the skin and have certain advantages as they deliver a therapeutically effective amount of drug through the patient's skin. Transdermal administration has the advantage over injections and oral routes of administration. It provides high patient compliance and avoids the disadvantage of oral administration by eliminating fast-pass metabolism.

Figure 2 Steps For Medicated Tattoo

INDICATION OF COMPLETE DRUG ABSORPTION:-

- There is a visual indication as to when the drug absorption starts and when it is completely absorbed into the skin.
- For this purpose, the manufacturer provides a color chart that compares the colors of the medicated tattoo applied to the patient as it

determines when the tattoo should be removed.

- Upon absorption, the tattoos gradually fade away and are painless to remove with the help of simple astringent wash containing
- The drugs used in medicated tattoos have some prototype drugs as Acetaminophen, vitamin C, etc.

Figure 3 Medicated Tattoo With Drug Allergy

Advantages of Medicated tattoos:

1. The main advantage of medical tattoos is the administration of medications to children who cannot tolerate the conventional dosage form.
2. They are very attractive & easy to wear because they are applied by wetting them with water and pressing them against the skin with a small force.
3. It improves the final appearance of the skin.
4. They nourish the skin as many are specially formulated with nutrients and vitamins to improve and speed up the healing process.
5. It prevents infections, as moisturizing the tattooed area prevents the formation of scabs and seals the wounds so that bacteria cannot spread.

Disadvantages of Medicated tattoos:

There are potential health risks and complications associated with tattooing such as infections, tattoo-related dermatoses, and allergic reactions:

1. There is a risk of developing cancer because it contains carcinogens.
2. There is a risk of getting hepatitis due to the use of needles.
3. In addition, the insertion of the needle into the skin is associated with pain.
4. There are cases of skin rashes.

TYPE OF INK IS USED FOR MEDICAL TATTOOS:-

There are many types of ink that can be used for medical tattooing depending on the application. Often for medical bracelets and many of the

restoration work, most clients just up to go with their own choice of colors and will either choose organic or traditional inks. Traditional inks use the following to make the colors:

- Mercury for red
- Lead for yellow, green or white
- Cadmium for red, orange or yellow
- Nickel for black
- Zinc for yellow or white
- Chromium for green
- Cobalt for blue
- Aluminum for green or violet
- Titanium for white
- Copper for blue or green
- Iron for brown, red or black
- Barium for white

For the markers that are tattooed on for medical reasons during radiation using a medical grade tattoo ink. This is mostly just to make sure it is intact for the radiation work. The kit will also come with different colors to identify different treatment spots and intensity.

The Formulation of Medicated Tattoos:-

The formulation & composition of tattoos:

- A drug layer
 - A color design layer
 - An adhesive layer (binds to the skin)
1. A tattoo patch is loaded with medication and is usually adhered to the skin to deliver a specific dose of medication through the skin into the bloodstream. The adhesive has two main functions: It is the adhesive that holds the patch to the skin, and it acts as a suspension that holds the drug.
 2. The problem with this is that the concentration of the drug in the adhesive directly affects the "stickiness" of the adhesive. Thus, if large amounts of the drug are to be administered, either the size of the patch must be increased, or the patch must be repeatedly reapplied.

3. The drug candidate, as well as other drugs, are usually combined with substances such as alcohol in the patch to improve their penetration through the skin and thus absorption. They are also applied in the same way to clean, dry skin.
4. Tattoos are temporary to permanent markings in the skin, usually done with ink and needle. Once the ink has penetrated the dermis, the second layer of skin scrapes over it; then the skin heals, exposing the design under the new layer of skin. When it is completely healed, it is a beautiful tattoo on the body. This is the concept of natural tattooing. A tattoo fades when the immune system manages to dissolve the pigment particles.
5. The concept of "medical tattooing" is very similar to traditional tattooing, except that here non-allergic ink is placed in the dermal (deeper) layers of the skin.
6. "Medical tattooing is also recommended for patients who have undergone breast reconstruction and has proven to be a better and more effective delivery system. At the same time, women use medical tattoos to cover scars left on the breast after surgery.
7. Tattoo-based drug delivery systems are also used to treat cutaneous leishmaniasis. Tattoos are widely used in medical research to implement the concept of DNA vaccination strategy. Medical tattooing (Med-Tat) is a variation of temporary tattooing that contains an active agent for transdermal delivery.
2. A tattoo patch is loaded with an active drug and applied to the skin to deliver a specific drug dose across the skin to achieve the desired therapeutic effect.
3. It contains an adhesive that ensures the patch sticks to the skin and also serves as a suspension for the drug.
4. The manufacturer provides a color chart that can be compared to the color of the patient's tattoo to determine when the tattoo should be removed.
5. The important visual comparison depends on the dyes incorporated into the patch, resulting in significant variability between patients.

Applications of Medical Tattooing:-

Medical tattooing usually has one of the following two objectives:

1. restoration, which is the addition of pigment to restore the appearance of the dermis so that it approximates its pre-disease state and blends with the surrounding skin
2. camouflage, which is the addition of an aesthetically pleasing artistic image or pattern to hide surface defects or blemishes. Both applications of tattooing have cosmetic and restorative goals in a medical context.

APPLICATIONS

Scalp Tattooing:-

Common medical tattoo application is to add pigment to the scalp in cases of advanced male pattern baldness and alopecia. The goal of medical tattooing of the scalp is to provide the illusion of the appearance of hair follicles in areas with hair loss, including scars. Two studies were identified which describe this application and provide meaningful outcome data.

The Basic Mechanism behind Medicated Tattoo:-

1. It is applied to clean and dry skin.

Figure:-4 Shaved Hair-Style Scalp Tattoo On A 34-Year-Old Male With Norwood Stage 5 Alopecia. (A) Before Top View, (B) Before Front View, (C) After Top View, And (D) After Front View.

Vitiligo:-

Vitiligo is a medical condition in which the cells that produce melanin stop functioning, causing the skin to lose pigment, turning white. Vitiligo occurs in approximately 1% of the population. This skin disorder affects all races, although it is more noticeable in darker pigmented skin because of the contrast between the affected area and unaffected

areas. The goal of micropigmentation in patients with vitiligo is the restoration of the appearance of skin color. That is to add pigment to blend the affected areas in with the surrounding skin tone. The challenge is to achieve the best pigment color match possible. One study was identified which describes medical tattooing procedures for vitiligo and provide successful outcome data.

Figure 5:-Vitiligo Of The Fingers On A 56-Year-Old Female (A) Before The Procedure And (B) Just After The Procedure.

Three-dimensional (3D) restorative tattooing has the goal of providing an illusion of the pre-morbid appearance of the dermis. The skill and experience level required to execute 3D restorative tattoos are much higher than just adding color to the pigment. Matching skin tones is the basis of restorative treatment for conditions of hypopigmentation, but it is expanded on in 3D tattooing by utilizing light and shadow with pigments to create the illusion of depth in the dermis where there is none. The most

commonly studied restorative tattoos have been with patients with a history of breast cancer needing nipple-areola complex (NAC) reconstruction tattoos.

NAC Restorative Tattoos:-

The treatment of breast cancer often requires surgeries, which can result in the removal of one or both NACs. Medical tattooing offers a unique solution to the issue of the missing NAC, either in combination with different nipple reconstruction

techniques or as a “tattoo only” option by creating a 3D image in the place of a reconstructed nipple.

Ten studies were found that evaluated patient satisfaction with the application of NAC tattooing.

Figure 6:- NAC Restorative Tattoos

TATTOOS FOR THE INDICATION OF THE DISEASE STATE FOR EMERGENCY HELP:-Tattoos can be used to indicate the disease state of a person to be helped in the disease states with critical time like in case of diabetes, epilepsy

and heart strokes. Hence, in this case, by looking at such tattoos, the medical emergency can be identified, and the patient should be immediately supported by the recommended health support.

Figure 7:- Tattoos For The Indication Of The Disease State For Emergency Help

Patient Satisfaction: -

Overall, patients reported high satisfaction for all conditions for which medical tattooing was used as an intervention. Follow-up time varied both within each disease category and across all diseases studied. The shortest average follow-up time was 2 weeks, and the longest average follow-up time was 38.5 months. The lowest average satisfaction rating was found for scar tattooing at 78% and the highest rating of 100% was found for NAC tattooing, vitiligo tattooing, and scalp tattooing.

Table 2 shows the overall patient satisfaction data per study.

Case Study:-

Drug Delivery by Tattooing to Treat Cutaneous Leishmaniasis

OIPC-liposomes induce dose-dependent killing of intracellular Leishmania in cultured macrophage-derived cell lines:

- Macrophage- derived cell lines were infected with ratios of 1 cell: 20 parasites or 1 cell:10 parasites of *L. major* or *L. mexicana* for 6 h and treated with indicated

concentration of OIPC-liposomes (OIPC-lipo) for 18 additional hours.

- Data are shown as mean percentage of Leishmania- infected macrophages (3–5 counts of 100 cells from a representative experiment out of 2 different experiments).

In vivo efficacy of OIPC-liposomes against L. major CL.

Female Blab/c mice received 10×10^6 stationary phase L. major promastigotes transfected with luciferase at the tail base. After 12 weeks, mice were treated 2 \times 5 days with PBS vehicle or OIPC-liposomes: 36–90 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$ administered with a tattoo device (tattoo), 30 mg/kg/day IP, or 900 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$ as a topical drop on the top of the lesion (topic). Lesions were measured from the start day of the treatment (Day 0) on individual pictures taken on Day 0, 7, 14, 21 and 28 for each mouse. Lesion areas were calculated using the Adobe Photoshop® software. Representative pictures of lesions from each group are shown in (a); mean lesion sizes ($\pm\text{SEM}$) up to Day 28 are presented in (b); $P < 0.05$ between treated (tattoo), (+IP) and vehicle groups ($n = 7-9$). Individual lesion sizes per group on Day 28

In vivo efficacy of OIPC-liposomes against L. mexicana CL.

Female Balb/c mice received 10×10^6 stationary phase L. mexicana promastigotes at the base of tail. After 12 weeks, mice were treated 2 \times 5 days with PBS vehicle or OIPC-liposomes (36–90 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$) administered with a tattoo device. Lesions were measured from the start day of the treatment (Day 0) from individual pictures taken on Day 0, 7, 14, 21 and 28 for each mouse. Lesion areas were calculated using the Adobe Photoshop® software. Representative pictures of lesions from each group are shown in (a), while mean lesion sizes ($\pm\text{SEM}$) up to Day 28 are presented in (b); (*) $P < <0.05$ between treated and vehicle groups ($n = 6$).

Conclusion Of Case Study

- This study demonstrates that the use of a tattoo instrument for drug delivery is possible in the treatment of cutaneous leishmaniasis, and that this method can successfully eliminate intracellular parasites at the site of infection.
- The data support the idea that the mode of administration of a drug can impact its efficacy, suggesting that drugs already approved for the treatment of cutaneous leishmaniasis could be repositioned to be delivered with a tattoo instrument, owing a proper formulation.

Complications and Future Directions:-

- Complications were reported in some studies, but most were resolved without further intervention. The most commonly reported complications were erythema (skin irritation), edema, initial hyperpigmentation, and slight fading of the pigment. Other complications included minor reactions to the dressing, scar dehiscence, infection, rash, and eschar. Of particular interest is the issue of fading tattoos. It is not clear why some tattoos are more resistant, and others fade more quickly. In general, our experience has been that most tattoos last about 10 years before a touch-up or additional treatment is needed. We have encountered tattoos that fade more quickly, and we suspect that sun exposure is the primary cause; however, this has not been empirically studied. The brand of ink used may vary in terms of resistance to fading. Unfortunately, the existing studies do not specify which brand was used. We are aware of some proprietary inks being advertised as supposedly better for medical tattoos. Such claims about proprietary inks must be evaluated in independent empirical studies, and if these inks are marketed for medical applications, they must be evaluated by the

Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for performance and safety.

- Adequate information about the instruments, the inks, the person doing the tattooing, and the techniques is rarely available. For example, it is our impression that many of the tattoos performed by physicians in practice are sometimes performed using surface abrasion techniques, whereas those performed by medical tattoo assistants and other tattoo artists use skin penetration techniques. The relative effectiveness of these techniques needs to be studied empirically. It is our impression that surface abrasion techniques result in more scarring, making touch-up and post-treatment more difficult.
- The use of cultured melanocytes has been used successfully in the treatment of vitiligo.²⁸ A recent 2019 article by Tsao et al used surgically transplanted melanocytes to fuse white scars to the surrounding skin.²⁹ However, the use of cultured melanocytes using tattooing devices is speculative at this time, and the costs of such an approach may outweigh the benefits. Such advances would require that the procedure be performed in the dermatologist's or plastic surgeon's office.

CONCLUSION

Medical tattoos as a transdermal drug delivery system have been recognized as a potential delivery system despite their limitations. This delivery system allows rate-controlled drug delivery with fewer side effects, increased efficacy, and consistent delivery. Human skin has been shown to have extremely good barrier function, and to improve drug penetration, it is often necessary to use enhancement strategies. In addition, tattooing has gained tremendous popularity in the medical field. Tattooing is increasingly used for medical identification of diseases that require special attention in emergencies, such as diabetics who are

unconscious due to hypoglycemia or patients with allergy to a specific drug. In the current edition, the treatment options for tattoos are well described, and in addition, individualization is required to address the patient's safety concerns. It serves as a reliable and effective tool for the treatment of laymen, professionals, beauticians and traumatized people. Moreover, the inclusion of non-toxic and non-irritating biodegradable vegetable pigments in medical tattoos can cause an explosion in medical science.

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HOW TO CITE: Shaikh Naumaan Naeem , Pradnya Palekar Shanbhag , Aseem Ramsamujh Jaiswar , Chirag Laxmikant Rane , Manishkumar Prajapat , Vanshika K. Sahu, A Comprehensive Review on Assessment of Adulteration Detection Techniques In Edible Oils, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 9, 1123-1131. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13825045>

